

IDENTIFYING TRAINING REQUIREMENT OF NON-TEACHING STAFF OF SELF-FINANCE INSTITUTIONS

Dr. Shobha Dedhia

HOD, Department of Commerce,

Smt. MMP Shah Women's College of Arts & Commerce, Mumbai

INTRODUCTION

‘Non-teaching staff’ is a category defined as anyone employed by a school system who doesn't serve as a classroom teacher. This can include administrative staff, guidance counselors, librarians, custodians, food service personnel, and even transportation workers. Teaching and non-teaching staff are the two essential workhorses of any academic institution. It is essential for the non-teaching staff to perform their duties responsibly to enable the teaching staff and the organization to work smoothly. They both have to work in synchronization with each other to make the organization grow. People in education have greater needs for conceptual, human relations skills as well as job related skills. Therefore, their need for training does not remain confined to the development of skills needed for specific jobs.

Earlier the function of training was very simple - a person selected by an organisation was trained so that he fitted into the job he was appointed for and employers start extracting the services of the employee. This was primitive concept of training. With the changes in values and many other factors, the trend has changed. Training is viewed as an ongoing lifelong cyclical process.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The specific objectives are as below:

- To study if any training is at all provided to non-teaching staff of self-finance Institutions
- To study the current trend and awareness about the training of non-teaching staff of the educational institutions, special reference to self-finance Institutions.

- To identify the areas in which the training is to be imparted to these staff and prepare a list of training programmes so required.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

Following inferences have been drawn as the basis of starting point for this study:

1. It is assumed that training and development programmes can bring in the positive change in the behavior and efficiency of the employees at work. This change usually has a focus on knowledge or information, skills or activities, attitudes or beliefs and value system.
2. It is believed that spread of training opportunities among teaching and non-teaching staff is not even.
3. It is believed that although authorities (employers/management) are aware of the benefits of training programmes, required resources are not directed towards that end in case of self-finance Institutions of India.

FINDINGS

1. Profile of employees

The profile of majority of employee offers a cross-section of dimensions with variations as below.

Sr. No.	Criteria	Percentage
1	Educational qualification	
	Under graduates	52
	Graduates	43
2	Experience	
	05 to 10 years	48
	10 years & above	22
3	Nature of job	
	Administrative	52
	Accounts & clerical	13
4	Formal Training obtained	
	Yes	35
	No	65

PROFILE OF EMPLOYEES

Table: 1.1

Most of the staff members of an educational institution under the study are under graduates & graduates. Many of them are working for up to 10 years or even more than that. Majority of them perform general administrative work. Notable point here is, majority of members have not obtained any formal training related to the job they perform. This indicates that the general work is carried out in an unorganized manner.

2. Areas to be strengthened for better work culture

Figure: 1.1

Majority of the respondents are not clear on the specific job that they have to perform. While interacting with the employees, it was observed that there is overleaping of work assigned to them. Even they believe that they have been assigned job randomly and not in accordance with their caliber & potential. All this makes them feel that the work culture needs planning and organizing to have proper work distribution and smooth flow of work.

Respondents also feel to have support where by strong ‘team sprit’ gets developed and relationship among themselves as well as with third party (outsiders) get strengthened.

Respondents need some guidance in the fundamentals of accounts related to their nature of job. Some of them do perform the job though they have not obtained any formal training in it. In the opinion of few members, computer training will form a support.

3. Faith/ Trust in training.

Opinion of the respondents on significance of training programme based on their past experience (if any) as well as with the perception of obtaining the required training

in future was arrived at. Data collected on the positive approach towards the training is indicated below.

Faith / Trust in Training

Figure: 1.2

Majority of the members believe that right training will help them to strengthen in specific areas related to their job.

4. Priority of areas requiring training

Though many of the respondents come across university/ board/ departmental rules regulations, guidelines, circulars etc. in their day-today functioning, they believe that result is not as per expectation, as rules, procedures, system keeps changing which lends them up with confusion. They need proper guidance especially on those matters which are to be handled for the first time.

As per the data gathered while interviewing some of the respondents, training in the areas of 'Team Building' tops the list. Lack of harmony in work/ work culture is felt by majority of the respondents. Need for training in 'Group Dynamics' is the result of it. Respondents desire to develop the team spirit for better performance.

Heavy work pressure & fast life of 'Mumbaikar and Pune-kars' push them to learn the techniques of 'Time Management' & 'Stress Management'. To be effective at communication as well as sound knowledge of computers and maintaining better office system is also at priority. Most of the respondents do need to get acquainted with crisis management, managing change & building their capacity, but all these are at bottom of the priority list.

Recommendations:

1. There is a strong need of correlating the training activity with vision, mission & objectives of the institution and have a strategic planning in this regard.

Training aligned with vision, mission & objectives of the institution

2. It is recommended that the Director/Principals should address the non-teaching staff at regular intervals and provide direction in line with vision, mission & objectives of the institution. This will motivate the employees to get trained, bridge the gap and also implement the learning acquired from the training.

Providing direction to get trained

- 3 The institution should develop a fixed policy guideline of training programme and monitor the implementation of it on a regular basis. There is also a need of allocating funds for such purpose. Yearly detailed training schedule (training calendar) should be prepared. Institutions can arrange programmes in-house with the help of internal faculties being resource person or inviting the professional experts.

Policy guideline and provision of funds for training

- 4 It is strongly suggested to execute 'job description' exercise and others should be made aware about the same. It is also required to be adhered strictly.

Job description is a must

- 5 About 22% of non-teaching staff members have more than 10 years' experience. This group of members should be trained to train the less experienced staff. Available senior staff should provide on-the-job training to the juniors.

Training the seniors who will train the juniors

- 6 When there is an invitation by other institute to attend a workshop or training session, an 'eligible' employee should be deployed instead of a 'spare' employee. Members should also be sponsored for the required training programmes organized by the external agencies.

More exposure & training to the right candidate

- 7 Identifying the talent of in-house teaching faculty and competent students can support the training activity in a great way. In addition to this external expertise can also be used in relevant area.

Developing internal force of trainers & engaging external experts

- 8 Work related training programmes (technical) can be organized by some of the Institutions taking initiative. e.g. 'Administrative procedures to start and run self-

finance courses’

Institutions to take initiatives in organizing programmes

9 Developing feedback and evaluation system with the help of instruments like pre-post test, interview, change in performance etc. is required. It will make training programme justifiable and meaningful. Right feedback system will also develop interest among the participants and will make them more sincere towards implementation of learning from training.

Conclusion:

The words ‘Training & Development’ relates more with the corporate world. Heavy investments made by corporate in training programmes have been reflected in the positive results. The theory of methodical training can work positively with non-teaching staff of educational institutes also. A concerted effort to train, educate & develop employees will help lead towards fulfillment of the objectives of the institution. Training programmes can be customized according to the need identification and analysis. Such programmes benefit the individuals, groups as well as the institution. The wave of the future is breaking on the shore. High competition amongst various educational institutes, thrust to achieve quality and accomplishment of various parameters of success are possible with combined efforts of management as well as staff at all levels.

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